

STRATEGIES OF OVERCOMING TOXIC WORK-ENVIRONMENT AND EFFECTIVE TEAM BUILDING IN LOCAL COMPANIES

Vazira Abdulloyeva¹, Yakubova Madina²

^{1,2}“Silk Road” International University of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

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Abstract. *The best way of achieving success easily is having a relationship in team that everyone works in a harmony and fulfills each other's mistakes. This article suggests the ways of reducing toxic work environment, building friendly team in local companies of Uzbekistan. Most of the business owners in Uzbekistan do not consider the importance of team-building and they pay attention to profit they make. By reading this article some of the strategies of top CEO's of the world can be known. If those strategies are used appropriately, the result can be outstanding.*

Key words: *Team-building, Uzbek companies, toxic work environment.*

Annotatsiya. *Oson va samarali muvaffaqiyatga erishishning eng yaxshi yo'li – bu jamoada bir-birini to'ldiradigan va uyg'un ishlaydigan munosabatlarni shakllantirishdir. Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonning mahalliy kompaniyalarida toksik ish muhitini kamaytirish va do'stona jamoa tuzish yo'llari taklif etiladi. O'zbekistondagi ko'plab tadbirkorlar jamoaviy ishning ahamiyatiga e'tibor bermay, faqatgina foydaga e'tibor qaratadilar. Ushbu maqolani o'qish orqali dunyoning eng yaxshi ish boshqaruvchilarning ba'zi strategiyalari bilan tanishish mumkin. Agar bu strategiyalar to'g'ri qo'llansa, natijalar nihoyatda a'lo bo'lishi mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Jamoa tuzish, O'zbek kompaniyalari, adovatli ish muhiti.*

Аннотация. *Лучший способ легко добиться успеха — это построение таких отношений в команде, при которых все работают в гармонии и компенсируют ошибки друг друга. В данной статье предлагаются способы снижения токсичной атмосферы на рабочем месте и построения дружной команды в локальных компаниях Узбекистана. Большинство владельцев бизнеса в Узбекистане не придают значения тимбилдингу и сосредоточены на получении прибыли. Прочитав эту статью, можно узнать некоторые стратегии ведущих генеральных директоров мира. При правильном применении этих стратегий можно достичь выдающихся результатов.*

Ключевые слова: *тимбилдинг, узбекские компании, токсичная рабочая атмосфера.*

The research topic I chose focuses on advising strategies of leadership in developed countries to Uzbekistan. Overall 5 articles used as a source for research explains how leaders and HR managers work around the world. Firstly, the article called “Reducing workplace incivility” (Laschigner&Wong,2014) explains the importance of strategic leadership and why is it important and examines several of the typical aspects of strategic leadership, adds several other critical behavioral aspects such as focusing on the core message and strategy; disseminating the strategy in the organization; developing and sensitizing employees to strategic issues; integrating the right people, technology and strategy; building ownership and trust; and reinforcing the core message and strategy by linking shared leadership, organizational culture and key performance indicators. Second article, written by Brian&Gartner in 2021 is called “What does it mean to be a manager today?” gives information about importance of empathy in managerial sphere, as it says ‘empathy

requires developing high levels of trust and care and culture of acceptance within teams. The next article, “The toxic handler: organizational hero and casualty” by Katzenbach & Smith in 1991, is quite similar to the one as mentioned above, it analyses the Slovenian company called “Sakhuna” in terms of team control and accepting workers from around the world. In this company leader faces with difficulties to deal with employees, to make deeper research I found another quote specifically for overcoming toxic work environment, according to Massarik (2013, as cited in Brian & Gartner, 2024), leadership is having interpersonal influence in a particular situation, using communication to guide towards achieving specific goals. The last article is about mistakes that are usually made by leaders and human resource managers. Using all the resources that are mentioned above, Uzbek companies need to apply strategies of top companies in order to improve.

In recent years the number of companies in Uzbekistan is increasing, and this development is beneficial for providing workplaces for unemployed citizens. Every company has to deal with specific problems related to relationship between staff, accounting or budgeting. Although, financial problems can be tackled with correct mathematical ways and strategies, maintaining friendly team and hiring the best candidate among others might be quite challenging. In order to increase work efficiency heads of the company: CEOs, HR managers, leaders should adopt strategies of worldwide, developed companies which successfully deal and set mutual goal with people from different cultural mindsets and behaviors. Maintaining friendly work environment is mainly leaders and human resource managers task and the quote mentioned by Whitener and his coworkers in 1998 says “leadership in controlling working conditions is crucial for organizations seeking to attract, retain, and effectively utilize the highest quality workers”. This research paper aims to suggest several ways of overcoming toxic work environment and creating team that looks to the same direction.

In developed countries of the world most of the huge companies are led by enthusiastic, empathic leaders, our country can also develop some of their strategies. The statement mentioned by Brian & Gartner in 2021 says that: “To be successful in this new environment, leaders must lead with empathy”. Empathy is one of the key factors of building team that is supportive and understanding. To be an empathic leader, person should develop high levels of trust, care and a culture of acceptance within teams. Leader should know how to tie connections between employees, understand and support them in hard times, know how to explain in easier and accurate way when some changes are made in a company. Firstly, according to Morgan team is defined as “distinguishable set of two or more individuals who interact interdependently and adaptively to achieve specified, shared and value objectives”. Building this kind of team with Uzbek people with strong adaptation to culture, traditions might be quite challenging for the leaders. The most common problem of majority of Uzbek citizens is, they fail to understand the importance of doing the things that they have never done before, the ones that may be considered wrong because of strong cultural setting. These may include being afraid of getting out of comfort zone, being used to bureaucratic working environment, not being able to work in the team. Those problems can be tackled with the strategy founded by Cheung S.O called “From work-centered to employee-centered”. According to this strategy leaders and heads of the company pay attention to increase team quality, how well workers cooperate with each other, how satisfied they are from the working conditions. Cheung believes that when employees are satisfied with the facilities they have, work atmosphere and salary, the quality of service or production increases automatically. This method works really well in my country, thus most of the employers care more about the profit, quantity of product sold rather than employee satisfaction. Developing empathy in relationships may

increase employee satisfaction. “Leaders` motivation to be empathic increases when they have a support system that makes it clear that the burden is not theirs alone and when organization invest in roles designed to support them” (Brian&Gartner,2021). Team friendliness is built by both employers and employees, when both sides try to understand each other and be responsible of what they do the process of turning team to supportive, motivated and enthusiastic becomes easier. Another strategy that leads to improvement is, giving feedback in a way that does not make person feel disappointed. Statement by Usman (2018) says: “Giving employees constructive feedback allows them to grow as individuals while creating a more harmonious work atmosphere for the organization and its employees. It is important to review performance against these guidelines regularly and provide follow-up feedback to improve their performance if they respond positively”. So, overall leaders and CEOs of local companies should do some research and adapt above mentioned strategies.

Developing supportive team needs to overcome toxic work environment. According to Laschigner and his colleagues (2014) “A toxic work environment refers to the extent of negative behaviors, such as discrimination, bullying, colleague aggression, or other harmful that are present in a workplace, which can result in higher work related anxiety and stress”. In a toxic work environment employees are subjected to verbal, physical or emotional abuse from teammates or leadership resulting in hostility and conflict. “Pulling people down, being a passive-aggressive leader, spreading rumors that hurt one, playing dirty politics and being all aggressive are all examples of toxic behaviors”(Brian & Gartner,2021). I have interviewed workers about examples of toxic working environment and here is the results.

Table 1:

Survey from employees voting to types of toxic work environment

Examples of toxic work environment	Percentages of people voted for existence of these behaviors
Gender discrimination	39,8%
Age discrimination	28,9%
Emotional abuse	27,3%
Others	4%

Note: Research held among textile and pastry factory workers shows percentages of different toxic work environments.

There some strategies of reducing percentages mentioned above, however the one that is considered to be more powerful than others is “Bottom2top”. This strategy suggests the way of reducing age and gender discrimination as giving most important tasks to those that are mostly discriminated by others, for example when new, young and inexperienced employee joins to the theme where everyone is professional, with many years of experience, leader should give crucial tasks to the newcomer, so this person is valued and respected. The same strategy works when gender discrimination occurs. Tasks that are usually done by men should be given to women to make everyone realize both sexes have the same intellect, ability and responsibility. Another strategy that also works well not only in our country, but also in every company of the world - having traditions. This may include celebrating everyone`s birthday, international or traditional holidays, having a day when everyone gathers together to discuss future goals and giving feedbacks in a pleasant way. These occasions make employees and employers get to know each other well and everyone can learn new skills, information with each other.

In conclusion, future of company is depended on how well team is formed, before taking any steps for company’s improvement, main focus should be employee satisfaction, facilities available, friendly relationships between employee and employer. When above mentioned steps are taken, the team may be as mentioned by Katzenbah & Simith (1991) “a team is a small numbers of individuals associated in some joint action, with a strong, deep seated, common sense of purpose”. In the future, empathic leaders can change whole working atmosphere from boring nine-to-five job to the satisfactory process.

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